

Strategic development of environmentally friendly agriculture in respect to climate change adaptation and mitigation in Japan

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Greenhouse Gases and Global Warming

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Effects of Global Warming

- Without adaptation, local temperature increases in excess of about 1°C above pre-industrial is projected to have negative effects on yields for the major crops (wheat, rice and maize) in both tropical and temperate regions.

(IPCC AR5 WG2 Chapter 7, 2014)

Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU)

- The AFOLU sector is responsible for just under a quarter of anthropogenic GHG emissions, mainly from deforestation and agricultural emissions from livestock, soil and nutrient management.

Greenhouse Gas Emissions by Economic Sectors

(IPCC AR5 WG3 SPM, 2014)

Major Research Activities on Impact assessment & Adaptation

- Improvement of **rice productivity and quality** as adaptation options
- Agro-Meteorological Grid Square Data System (AMGSDS) for **weather forecast**
- Free-Air CO₂ Enrichment (**FACE**) experiments for rice
- **Modeling** rice production in response to climate change for evaluating future production

Agro-Meteorological Grid Square Data System (AMGSDS) for weather forecast

- Issues a weather warning, e.g., cold and heat damages.
- Recommends appropriate farm management, e.g., fertilizer application.

The Agro-Meteorological Grid Square Data

The system produces and distributes daily agro-meteorological grid (approx. 1 km) data, which seamlessly links observed values since 1980, up to 26 days of numerical forecasts, and climatic normal values.

Data Service and User Support

Users can acquire data for any spatiotemporal range from the dedicated server.

Technical supports by wiki and mailing list are available as well.

Negative effects of elevated CO₂ on the grain quality

- The increment in rice yield by elevated CO₂ was suppressed by high temperature.

- The presence of chalky grain was increased by high temperature.

Simulation Results for Future Rice Production in Japan

- Rice quality in 2081-2100 based on 4GCM
- Changes in the proportion of high quality rice to total production
- Based on the risk for heat stress index during 20 days after heading

- Future warming may significantly decrease rice quality in many regions
- Changing dates of transplanting may reduce the risk

Impact on Orchards

- ✓ **Insufficient or delayed coloring of maturing-stage apple and grape fruits**

Poor coloring of apples and grape fruits

- ✓ **In citrus mandarin orange, “peel puffing” due to high temperature and frequent rains, and sun burn of fruits due to higher temperature and intense solar radiation**

citrus “unshu”
“Peel puffing” (left)
Normal fruit (right)

- ✓ **Impacts of high temperatures in summer are reported as follows: a fall in milk yields, milk constituent and reproductive performance of dairy cows, and a fall in the rate of gain of beef cattle, pigs, and chickens.**
- ✓ **A declining feedstuff intake caused by rising temperatures in the summer time will bring more impact on the growth of pigs and chickens.**

Major Research Activities on Mitigation

- Modeling stock change of **soil organic carbon** based on long-term field experiments over the economy
- Reducing **methane and nitrous oxide emissions** from rice cultivation by alternative water management
- Greenhouse gas mitigation in irrigated rice paddies in Southeast Asia (**MIRSA project**)

Long-Term Experiments in Japan

○ Since 1975, the MAFF has conducted long-term experiments with continuous organic matter application under typical soil type and cropping system of each prefecture (over 150 sites in total), which demonstrated that soil carbon stock increased through organic matter application such as compost.

ta: "Basic Survey of Soil Environment (Benchmark Survey)" Yamaguchi Pref. Agricultural Research Institute. Figure for a year is the three-year average including the previous and the next year to that year.

T. Ota, NARO (2011)

Rice Paddies: A major source of methane

- Rice paddies represent a globally important source of atmospheric methane (CH₄).
- Estimates of CH₄ emissions from rice paddies are equivalent to ~11% of the global anthropogenic CH₄ emissions (IPCC, 2014).
- In order to meet the increasing demand for rice production of the world, rice paddies will continue to be an important CH₄ source in the near future.

How we can mitigate CH₄ emissions from a rice paddy?

- Methanogens are strict anaerobic archaea, and thus their activity is enhanced under reductive conditions in a flooded paddy soil.
- In contrast, methanogens are significantly inhibited under oxidative conditions caused by draining practices.

AWD: Alternate Wetting and Drying

As far as I know, the term “AWD” is now used as a common term that denotes “water management practice during rice growing period.”

In our project, the three practices are shared and tested at all the sites.

- 1. Continuous flooding:** as reference practice
- 2. Safe AWD:** naturally drained until the surface water table reaches -15 cm; and then irrigated...
- 3. Site-specific AWD:** established based on scientific experience of each monitoring site (i.e., can differ in the practice among the sites)

MIRSA Project
 (Greenhouse Gas Mitigation in Irrigated Rice Paddies in Southeast Asia)

